

CRACK GROWTH IN A PIEZOELECTRIC CERAMIC INDUCED BY A CYCLIC ELECTRIC FIELD

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In piezoelectric materials, an electric charge is generated in response to an applied mechanical stress (piezoelectric effect). Vice versa, given an applied electric field, these materials will show elastic deformation (inverse piezoelectric effect). In the case of high electric driving fields, cyclic electrical loading can cause electrical and mechanical degradation, such as the initiation and growth of cracks. In this study, commercial hard-PZT (lead zirconate titanate) discs are pre-damaged by a Vickers indent and subjected to cyclic electrical loading with a high electric field. Fatigue crack growth is monitored until fracture occurs. Fatigue life until fracture is displayed in a Weibull plot, showing three classes of failure (early, intermediate and late). Fracture surfaces are observed postmortem through scanning electron microscopy.

Keywords: piezoelectric ceramic, Vickers indentation method, fatigue crack propagation, fatigue life

INTRODUCTION

The piezoelectric effect is a phenomenon of piezoelectric ceramics. In these materials, an applied mechanical stress generates an electrical charge. This effect is particularly used in sensor applications. The reversal of this is the inverse piezoelectric effect, in which an applied electric field causes a mechanical strain. In the case of a cyclic electric field, a mechanical oscillation is generated. This is used in piezoelectric actuators in high-power ultrasound (e.g. sonar) applications. Depending on the application, soft- or hard-doped piezoelectric ceramics are used. The terms "soft" and "hard" refer to the dipole or domain mobility and thus to the polarisation behaviour. Soft-doped are used in high-precision sensor- and actuator applications, hard-doped in high-power actuator (e.g. ultrasound for material processing) applications. Particularly in the latter case of high-power actuator applications, cyclic loading with large electric fields can lead to material degradation, such as fatigue and crack growth from internal defects.

The fatigue and damage behaviour of piezoelectric materials has been investigated using pre-cracked specimens which were subjected to cyclic electrical loading. Testing setups were designed in a way, that the cyclic straining from the inverse piezoelectric effect results in cyclic tensile loading on the crack faces. Pre-damage is caused by a notch (such as in Westram et al. [1]) or by a Vickers indent with cracks emanating from its diagonals (such as in Ferguson et al. and others [2-5]). In these studies, the effect of applied electric field strength on crack growth behaviour was investigated. It was found that for the soft-PZT materials tested, a minimum electric field strength of approximately 0.8 [1] to 0.9 E_c [3] (with E_c being the coercive field) is required for cracks to grow. In some studies it was observed that the cracks only grew to a certain length, which was dependent on the distance of the electrodes [2-4]. It is interesting to note, that in these studies, crack growth rates have been

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found to be independent of crack length. Crack propagation is reported to occur in a steady state condition.

In the present study, a hard-doped PZT material was pre-damaged by Vickers indentation and subjected to cyclic electrical loading until fracture. The influence of the indentation load (and the size of pre-damage caused thereby) on the crack growth behaviour and the fatigue life under subsequent cyclic electrical loading was investigated. Attention was also paid to whether observed irregularities in crack growth behaviour (temporary stagnation, acceleration or strong differences in crack length) can be associated with a prolongation or shortening of fatigue life.

METHODS

Discs of PIC 181, manufactured by *PI Ceramic GmbH (Germany)* were used in this study. PIC 181 is a hard-doped lead zirconate titanate (hard PZT) with a high mechanical quality factor and good temperature and ageing stability of the piezoelectric properties. It is used in high-power ultrasound and sonar applications. The coercive field of this material is $E_c = 1.9$ kV/mm, while polarisation is done at elevated temperatures. The discs were 20 mm in diameter and 1 mm in thickness. Thin electrodes (Cr/CuNi) with a thickness of less than 1 μm had been sputtered on the upper and bottom face using PVD thin layer technique. In our test setup, the use of specimens with a thin electrode is particularly important to keep artefacts to a minimum, as the indentation is made through the electrode and the crack length is measured as it appears on the electrode surface.

Prior to cyclic electrical loading, pre-damage was induced by a Vickers indentation (using a pyramid-shaped diamond indenter in a *KB Prüftechnik KB 250 BVRZ video system*) in the centre of the positively polarised disc surface. The indentation load was 98.07 N (HV 10). To investigate the effect of a smaller pre-damage, an additional set of specimens was indented with 49.03 N (HV 5).

Specimens were subjected to cyclic electrical loading using a setup with a high-voltage amplifier and a function generator, applying a 0 to +2 kV square wave (corresponding to a maximum electric field of $E = 2$ kV/mm) at a frequency of 1 kHz, Fig.1. In this setup, the applied electrical load is monitored by a voltage divider with voltage measurement and an oscilloscope.

FIGURE 1 Setup for cyclic electrical loading. For reason of clarity, indent and cracks are displayed larger than in reality.

In this setup, both the indentation pre-damage and the electrical contact (electrode) are located on the face of the disc. Under cyclic electrical loading, the disc expands radially. As a result, the cracks

starting at the corners of the indent are not subjected to pure mode-I (tensile) loading, but to mixed mode-I-II loading with superimposed shear.

To observe crack propagation, the cyclic electrical loading was stopped at specific intervals, the specimen was demounted and transferred to an optical microscope (*Olympus BX60 with an MPlanFL N 20x/ 0.45 BD objective lens*). Images of the crack were taken and crack length was measured using the *Olympus Stream Essentials software*. After measurement, the specimen was remounted in the fixture and cyclic electrical loading was continued. The specimens eventually failed by fracture. Fatigue life data were tested for the validity of a Weibull distribution.

After fracture, crack surfaces were observed in a *Carl Zeiss SEM EVO 40 XVP* scanning electron microscope. Element analyses of particles, artefacts and traces on fracture surfaces were performed using a *QUANTAX EDS* system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pre-damage caused by Vickers indentation

Specimens were pre-damaged by Vickers indentation to a load of 98.07 N (HV 10) or 49.03 N (HV 5). Both loads were sufficient to cause initial cracks, starting from the corners of the indent. In order to identify the type of these cracks, several indented specimens were polished and the connection of the cracks to the residual indent was observed, Fig. 2. In all indented specimens, both HV 5 and HV 10, Palmqvist cracks (Fig. 2c) were found. Cracks of Palmqvist type emerge as separate cracks from each corner of the indent and will be detached from the inverted pyramid of the indentation when the upper surface layer is removed by polishing. In contrast, half-penny cracks, extend across the diagonal of the indent from one crack tip to the other. Such cracks do not lose their connection to the indent when polished. For an illustration of a half-penny crack, see Fig 4 and Niihara et al. [6].

FIGURE 2 HV 10-Indent on the face of a piezo disc a) as indented, b) after polishing: crack and indent are disconnected, indicating the presence of a c) Palmqvist crack (schematic illustration).

The indentation-caused pre-damage of 30 indentations with HV 10 and HV 5 each, was characterised by measuring the length of the half-diagonal a and the length of overall crack c , measured from the center of the indent, Table 1.

TABLE 1 Statistical analysis of the pre-damage caused by each 30 indents of HV 10 and HV 5. Half-diagonal, a and crack length, c are measured as specified in Fig. 2c). (M = mean value, SD = standard deviation).

Indentation load	a (μm)	c (μm)	c/a ratio
49,03 N (HV 5)	M = 80 (SD = 1)	M = 155 (SD = 8)	M = 1.91 (SD = 0.20)
98,07 N (HV 10)	M = 113 (SD = 3)	M = 255 (SD = 26)	M = 2.22 (SD = 0.21)

The c/a ratio can be used as an indicator of crack type: for ratios below 2.5, Palmqvist cracks can be assumed to be present. Above 2.5, most likely, half-penny cracks have formed [6,7]. For both applied loads, the c/a ratio suggests a Palmqvist crack. At higher loads, the ratio increases, which agrees well with the findings in Ćorić et al. [8] and indicates, that further increase in indentation load would eventually produce half-penny cracks.

The parameters shown in Table 1 can be used to determine the indentation fracture toughness (Vickers indentation fracture, VIF) of ceramic materials, as the crack lengths are inversely proportional to the fracture toughness. For the material used here, such analysis will be provided elsewhere.

Weibull analysis of fatigue life

Growth of indentation cracks was observed under cyclic electrical loading. Failure occurred as a final fracture that separated the discs into two or more pieces. The fatigue life of cyclic electrically loaded specimens with HV 10 and HV 5 pre-damage was subjected to a two-parameter Weibull analysis. Figure 3a shows the number of electrical cycles to failure for the full set of twenty-three specimens, the best-fit line and the 90 % confidence interval (95 % and 5 % confidence limits). It can clearly be seen that the experimental data does not follow a regular Weibull-distribution of a homogeneous population. Under the assumption that a Weibull-distribution can be applied, the dataset rather forms three separate ranges of cycle numbers with different slopes and positions on the cycles-axis. Our interpretation of this is that our dataset comprises failures of three different causes or different circumstances of failure. Thus we distinguish three different classes of failure for a further differentiated analysis, as shown in Figure 3a: class 1 with five specimens that failed very early, a set of four specimens with intermediate failure forming class 2, and the majority of specimens that failed late and were classified in class 3. A separate Weibull analysis was performed for class 3, Figure 3b. It shows that if only the fourteen specimens that failed in class 3 ($4.17\text{E}7$ to $5.88\text{E}7$ cycles to failure) are considered, a Weibull distribution can be applied with good approximation.

Anticipating the results of the post-mortem SEM and EDS fracture surface analysis in chapter 3.5, the early failure of the class 1 specimens was probably caused by dielectric breakdown events, most likely triggered by high humidity in the un-air-conditioned laboratory, i.e., an external influence. (All specimens of class 1 had been tested in the same week of very humid and warm summer weather.) Therefore, if dielectric breakdown had not occurred, these specimens would probably not have failed this early, but would most likely have been in the late failure class. There are no such obvious correlations for the specimens in class 2. These few specimens form an intermediate group with no evidence of dielectric failure events on the fracture surface. The failure of the class 1 specimens is attributed to crack growth and ultimate fracture under cyclic electrical loading.

FIGURE 3 Weibull plots of electrical cycles to failure for specimens pre-damaged by HV 10 or HV 5 Vickers indentation. a) total set of all specimens tested, showing three classes of failure: 1-early, 2-intermediate, 3-late – Weibull distribution is not applicable (shape parameter $k = 2.099$, scale parameter $\lambda = 4.2281E7$), b) subset of specimens with late failure (class 3) – Weibull distribution can be applied with good approximation (shape parameter, $k = 12.902$, scale parameter, $\lambda = 5.3250E7$).

Comparing the failure classifications of HV 10 and HV 5 indented specimens, the smaller pre-damage caused by HV 5 indentation does not result in a significant change in fatigue life. HV 5 indentations are found in all three failure classes.

Crack growth under cyclic electrical loading

In the consideration of the crack propagation behaviour under cyclic electrical loading, in this study, cracks are considered to be of half-penny type. It is assumed, that Palmqvist cracks starting from the same diagonal soon coalesce below the indent to form such a semi-elliptical crack. Thus, crack length is measured from one tip of the crack, past the indent, to the other tip of the crack, see Fig. 4. This is in accordance with the definition of the crack length reported in [2,3].

FIGURE 4 Semi-elliptical (half-penny) crack geometry, as assumed for the crack propagation considerations. Measured crack lengths are referred to as “crack 1” and “crack 2” in Figure 5.

For an indented specimen under cyclic electrical loading, the growth of two orthogonal half-penny cracks was documented, each starting from a diagonal of the indentation.

Figure 5 shows typical crack growth behaviour for representative specimens, including late failure specimens (Figs. 5a and b), an early failure specimen (Fig. 5c) and a specimen with smaller pre-damage (i.e. after a lower-load indentation, HV 5, Fig. 5d). Please note, that crack length could not be measured or reconstructed for the moment of final fracture. Therefore, the fracture point is represented by a vertical dashed line at the corresponding number of cycles.

FIGURE 5 Crack growth data for two orthogonal cracks, each starting from a diagonal of the indentation (crack 1 and 2), and their average. Cracks are considered to be of half-penny shape and measured from one crack tip, past the indent, to the other crack tip. The final fracture point is marked by a dashed line. Crack growth data are given for representative specimens considering pre-damage load and failure class.

Crack growth in specimens #23 and #18 (Figs. 5 a and c) is homogeneous for both cracks. This is consistent with the loading conditions, which, by initiating cyclic radial expansion of the disc, causes a mixed-mode tension-and-shear loading at the crack faces. Due to symmetry, loading on both cracks is equal. Inhomogeneous crack growth has also been observed, as in specimens #16 and 8 (Figs. 5b and d). However, even exceptionally fast growth of one crack does not necessarily lead to early failure.

In terms of crack propagation rates, both continuous growth in a steady state (Fig. 5a) can be observed, as well as periods of stagnation, as for specimen #16 (Fig. 5b). Our results indicate that periods of stagnation cannot be associated with a significant increase in fatigue life.

Comparison of the HV 10 (Figs. 5a-c) and HV 5 (Fig. 5d) indented specimens shows that the average size of the initial crack is about 500 μm and 300 μm , respectively. However, this difference in crack length diminishes under cyclic electrical loading. For all observed HV 5 indented specimens, the initial cracks grew within the first $1\text{E}7$ cycles to a length similar to the crack length observed in HV 10 indented specimens. Thus, the size of the mechanically-induced crack (in the range observed in our study) does not affect the overall fatigue performance.

Crack propagation rates

Crack propagation rates were evaluated by dividing the increase in crack length in between two measurement points (da , using the average of crack 1 and 2) by the number of cycles in that period (dN). As the stress intensity range ΔK could not be easily determined due to the complicated mixed-mode loading condition, crack growth rates are displayed as a function of crack length.

Figure 6 shows crack propagation rates for specimen with different sizes of mechanical pre-damage (indentation by HV 10 or HV 5, respectively) and early or late failure. For a better overview, four specimens have been selected to give the overall picture and represent the range of crack propagation rates.

FIGURE 6 Crack propagation behaviour of representative selected specimens. Rates of crack propagation from HV 5 and HV 10 indentations are shown for early and late failure specimens. "Crack length" refers to the average crack length of crack 1 and 2 (cf. Fig 4 and 5).

Crack propagation rates are mainly in the range of 0.007 to 0.1 nm/cycle, occasionally even in the decade below. There is no dependence on crack length, but rather a "steady state" behaviour, as illustrated e.g. by specimen #23. This confirms what Ferguson et al. [3] and Cao and Evans [5] reported on the crack propagation behaviour. A comparison of two specimens with late failure after HV 10 indentation shows, that in this case the crack propagation rates can be quite stable throughout the entire process (specimen #23) or fluctuate over a wide range (specimen #16). Even the temporary presence of elevated crack propagation rates does not necessarily lead to early failure.

Significant differences between the crack propagation after HV 5 and HV 10 indentation cannot be inferred from the available data, although an accelerated crack propagation rate within the first $1E7$ cycles would have been expected for the HV 5 specimen. Presumably the crack length measurement method is too inaccurate due to the large increments chosen to allow further interpretation.

Comparison of our results with those reported in the relevant literature [1-5] is somewhat difficult, as most of the reported work deals with setups where the indented face is orthogonal to the electrodes, which results in pure mode-I loading on the crack faces and causes the crack to grow orthogonal to the electric field. In addition, the materials studied were all soft piezoelectrics. What was found under these conditions can be summarised as follows: There is a threshold for crack propagation under cyclic electrical loading. If the electric field strength is less than 0.9 of the coercive field E_c , there is little or no crack growth. If the field strength is high enough to induce crack growth, cracks will only grow to a certain length and then increase in width. The crack length limit is of the order of the electrode spacing [2-4]. Westram et al. [1] report that crack branching and secondary cracking occur at field strengths greater than $1.4 E_c$.

Our results on mixed-mode loading of a hard PZT confirm the presence of crack propagation for an electric field above E_c . However, in our test scenario the crack growth proceeds to the final fracture of the specimen. This is in agreement with Cao and Evans [5] who also report crack growth to fracture.

It has been reported [1,3,5] that the crack propagation rates do not depend on the crack length, but that the cracks grow in a steady state. This also shows in our results.

The influence of loading frequency is still under discussion. Ferguson et al. [3] reported that a higher loading frequency results in a longer final crack length. Lynch et al. [4] report on very little frequency dependence. In our tests, the loading frequency was in the kHz range, significantly higher than in the above studies. It is still unclear to what extent this contributes to deviations from the results cited above.

Fracture Surfaces

Figure 7 shows the fracture surfaces of one class 1 (early failure) and one class 3 (late failure) specimen in total view and with slightly higher magnification. EDS measurements were carried out for chemical analysis.

Below the indentations, shear cracks with an inclination of 30° to 45° can be seen in both specimens. The dark particles on the fracture surface are shreds of the electrode coating. EDS analysis shows that they contain Cu, Ni and Cr. In the early failure specimen (Fig.7a and c) such particles are scattered in a large number over the entire fracture surface. On the late-failure fracture surface, they are only present near the electrode faces. The early failure in class 1 is assumed to be due to a dielectric breakdown event, in which electrode fragments were scattered over the entire

fracture surface. Residues of carbon (detected by EDS measurements), present only on the fracture surface of the early-failed specimens, support this assumption. The large fragment attached to the Vickers indent above the fracture surface in the late-failure specimen (Fig.7d) is also electrode material (Cr/CuNi).

FIGURE 7 SEM of the fracture surfaces of each a representative specimen that failed early (a, c) or late (b, d), respectively.

In the early-failed specimen, a cavity can be seen in Fig.7c just below the surface, framed by coarse (electrode) particles. However, this cavity is too close to the indent to have caused the final fracture. The crack length measured from the indent was at least 170 μm when the specimen fractured. By this time, the crack front had already passed this void. It is also possible that this cavity was only created during the dielectric breakdown and final fracture.

The 'dielectric breakdown' failure mode identified for the five specimens in class 1 is probably also the reason why these specimens cannot be included in the Weibull distribution of the overall set of experiments. For the four class 2 specimens (intermediate failure), the cause of failure remains unclear, as it is not apparent from the fracture surface.

Fig. 8 shows images of the fracture surface at higher magnification to address the issue of crack growth morphology. In the studies of Cao and Evans [5], it is reported that cracks that develop under mechanical loading progress transgranularly, whereas cracks that develop under cyclic electrical loading progress intergranularly. Similar results are observed here: Fig. 7b, taken from a region where the crack grew under cyclic electrical loading, shows a clear intergranular path. Figure 7c shows the fracture surface immediately adjacent to the indentation, representing a fracture caused by mechanical loading during indentation. In addition to the intergranular areas, transgranular areas can also be seen here.

FIGURE 8 SEM images of the fracture surfaces a) overview of the vicinity of the Vickers indent; b) about 250 μm distant from the indent, produced by cyclic electrical loading, clearly showing intergranular crack growth; c) directly adjacent to the indent, produced by initial mechanical pre-damage, showing both crack growth morphologies, intergranular and transgranular.

SUMMARY

In this study, discs of PIC 181 hard PZT were pre-damaged by Vickers indentation and afterwards fatigued by cyclic electrical loading, resulting in crack growth and fracture. The results can be summarised as follows:

- All cracks induced by Vickers indentation with a load of 49.03 N (HV 5) and 98.07 N (HV 10) were Palmqvist type.
- Three classes of fatigue life under cyclic electrical loading were observed: 1-early, 2-intermediate, 3-late. For class 3, a Weibull distribution could be fitted with good approximation. Failure of class 3 specimens is attributed to crack growth and ultimate fracture under cyclic electrical loading, whereas early failure in class 1 is attributed to dielectric breakdown.
- Smaller size of pre-damage (in the range observed in our study, comparing HV 5 indentations to HV 10) does not result in a significant change in fatigue life.

- Crack growth under cyclic electrical loading proceeds in a steady state condition and is not affected by crack length. Referring to the homogeneity of crack growth, both equal length of cracks 1 und 2 are observed as well as significantly different crack lengths. Inhomogeneity of crack growth does not necessarily promote early failure.
- Periods of crack growth stagnation or of accelerated crack growth cannot be associated with a significant increase or decrease in fatigue life.
- Crack growth occurs intergranularly under cyclic electrical loading. Cracks induced by indentation (quasi-static mechanical loading) show both, trans- and intergranular features.

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